

ACTIVE CONTROL OF WING-ENGINE-SLAT-CUT-OUT REGION FLOW SEPARATION

Maayan Possti⁽¹⁾, Ariel Yaniv⁽¹⁾, Junaid Ullah⁽²⁾ and Avraham Seifert⁽¹⁾

⁽¹⁾ Meadow aerodynamics laboratory, School of Mech. Eng. Faculty of Eng. Tel Aviv University, Tel Aviv 69978, ISRAEL, Email: Seifert@eng.tau.ac.il

⁽²⁾ Institute of Aerodynamics and Gas Dynamics, University of Stuttgart, Pfaffenwaldring 21, 70569 Stuttgart, Germany, Email: ullah@iag.uni-stuttgart.de

ABSTRACT

This paper describes the CleanSky 2 project INAFLOWT. The project aims to investigate an innovative flow control concept, including steady suction and oscillatory blowing, to control the local flow separation taking place downstream of the slat cut-out over a generic high lift wing with integrated ultra-high bypass ratio flow-through engine. The wide slat cut-out causes premature flow separation. A team of five partners performed experiments and simulations on two differently scaled wind tunnel models in a collaborative environment. The baseline flow on the small-scale model has been found to be similar to the one on the large-scale model, despite differences attributed to Reynolds number and wind tunnel wall effects. This work focuses on the small scale experimental results of the baseline flow and the flow with activated steady suction. It is demonstrated that steady suction from nine discrete holes on the inboard side of the engine pylon at 1.5% chord location is capable to provide significant lift recovery, which is in agreement with CFD predictions. We present and discuss here the experimental effort and outline the route to the large-scale wind tunnel experiment, using steady suction and pulsed blowing, in an attempt to reduce the mass flow requirement and fulfil the performance recovery target.

1. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Fossil fuel is the most common energy source used to power aircraft and as a result engines emit polluting gases that also contribute to global warming. This fact along with increased use of aviation and the growth of ecological awareness forces the transportation industry to emphasize energy efficiency.

One possible remedy is increasing the bypass ratios and lowering the fan pressure ratios of turbofan aircraft engine, reducing the fuel consumption for the same thrust. Ultra-High Bypass Ratio (UHBR) engines are very effective from the fuel consumption aspect and therefore have great potential in civil aviation. On the

other hand, the engine's very large diameter leads to a challenging integration with the aircraft wing. UHBR engines positioned much closer to the wing due to the nacelle large diameter. This assembly requires a slat-cut-out in the area where the engine is connected. As a result, the wing experiences a local separation at the wing-engine junction due to the nacelle, pylon and the slat edges (Figure 1).

Active flow control (AFC) has great potential to postpone flow separation and reinstate degraded aerodynamic performance. The objective of the INAFLOWT project is to examine different AFC technologies in order to find a solution for the current UHBR engine – slat ends - wing integration. The current project follows the AFLONEXT project [1], in which the same problem was dealt with by pulsed blowing and “synthetic jets”. The main current task is to attempt and reduce the mass flow required by the pulsed jets to overcome the local separation and reinstate performance.

Figure 1 Separation on wing due to UHBR engine integration from [2][1]. Blue area marks regions with negative c_x values and thus indicates flow separation.

The SaOB actuator, that combines steady suction and pulsed blowing, is one possible route to reducing the mass flow requirement while providing similar performance gains [3]. To achieve that goal, a small-scale experiment, similar to

the large-scale test conducted within AFLONEXT, is performed in parallel to CFD simulations to predict performance. Once validated experimentally, the new innovative flow control concept will be applied on the same large scale set-up. This paper focuses on the experiments performed at Tel Aviv University (TAU). An accompanying paper describes the numeric effort and provides comparisons [4].

Figure 2 The GSM at TAU-WT looking downstream. The slats are in Blue.

Figure 3 A rear view of the GSM showing the main element and TE flap, turntables and flanges used as rotation axes.

Figure 4 A side view of the wing from the outboard side. The slats are in Blue.

2. EXPERIMENTAL SET UP

A Generic Small scale Model (GSM) scaled to 1:8.5 compared to the full-scale wing model tested as part of the AFLONEXT project [4][5] was built and tested at the Meadow Aerodynamics Laboratory, Tel-Aviv University. All tests described here were conducted at speed of 25m/s providing a Reynolds number of 0.640×10^6 .

The wing main element was fabricated from a 5mm thick fiberglass-epoxy with metal inserts where needed. The two slat parts, flap, nacelle and pylon were 3D printed in-house from PLA. The GSM width is 605mm (span) and the average chord length is 430mm (incl. slat and flap). The model was installed at the TAU Knapp-Meadow wind-tunnel (WT) with a test section of 607mm (W) X 1500mm (H) X 4250mm (L) (Figure 2). The nacelle large and small diameters are 236mm and 110mm, respectively, and the entire model creates a blockage ratio of 8% (of which 2.5% are due the nacelle addition to the wing) at AoA=0 (Figure 2).

A total of 190 steady pressure taps were installed in the GSM and on the WT walls and one unsteady pressure sensor is located close to the LE at the area of separation. A few chord length are used: it is 320 mm where the pylon is connecting, 295 mm otherwise (excluding the slats and flap). The average chord (including flap and slat) is 430 mm. All chords were measured normal to the LE direction. The chord for calculation of integral coefficients is 387 mm as well for experiments as for simulations. The slats are deployed to AoA of -28 deg and the flap setting is 35 deg. The airfoil was mounted between two circular Plexiglas and-plates (d=480mm) to enable AoA changing (Figure 2 and Figure 4) with the regular WT system.

On the wing, 158 static pressure taps were installed on the main element, two slats and flap. As shown in Figure 5, 119 of them on the main element in two span located cross sections (red, Figure 5), two rows in the spanwise positioned pressure taps (green, on the upper chamber) and 6 pressure taps located in the detachment expected region (yellow, termed front and back). On the two slats there were 27 pressure taps in two profile cross sections

(one on each slat close to the slat cut-out) and on the flap one profile cross section with 12 pressure taps. All pressure taps are drilled perpendicular to surface and instrumented with stainless tubes (OD=1mm, ID=0.7mm) reaching the aerodynamic surface and polished for smoothness. A total of 4 pressure tap bundles exit from the model, three on the inboard side and one on the outboard side (Figure 5).

Figure 5 The pressure taps locations on the main element, stream and span locations, slats and flap. Note that there is no one line of pressure taps around the entire wing.

Figure 6 The suction holes drilled at the un-protected inboard section of the LE. Hole diameter is 2mm and its spacing is 8mm. The most inboard hole is 1 and the most outboard is 9. Rows 1 and 3 from the CFD are drilled, row 2 omitted.

The total maximum length of the model is 935 mm in the X direction (free-stream direction). The GSM was assembled in the TAU Meadow-Knapp wind-tunnel [6] as shown in Figure 2. The GSM was finally connected to the sensor system and to the AoA setting rotary stage, installed at the outboard side of the model. Installing the GSM in the WT requires building it inside the test section from the main element, adding the nacelle only inside the test section.

Steady suction is a simple yet very effective AFC technique that is used for flow control. It was first presented by Ludwig Prandtl in 1904 [7]. Steady suction was widely studied, proven to be successful and showed great effect [8]. Localized suction was applied to the GSM for local separation control, as a first and easy step to locate its most efficient location and validate CFD results.

The design parameters of the AFC can have a great impact on the system performance [9][10]. Related to this project, the design parameters can be suction holes (or slots) location, its magnitude, flow control technique such as suction only, steady suction with or without alternating blowing, and more. Suction from holes at different locations (near the identified separation location) and variable suction magnitude were applied to the GSM.

Two rows of suction holes were drilled near the leading edge in the region of separation (Figure 6). These locations have also been simulated by the CFD partners of the project. Figure 6 shows the suction holes drilled in the model LE region. The first row (closest to the LE) is at about 0.016% x/c and the third row at 0.0457% x/c (termed third since in the CFD 3 rows were simulated). The holes are of 2 mm diameter and they are spaced 8 mm apart. In each row there are 9 holes, just on the inboard side of the Pylon.

Suction from the holes was generated by an external pump. The pump creates a sub-atmospheric pressure in the main element, otherwise sealed interior, that is used as a single suction cavity, which in turn creates suction flow through the holes.

Multiple suction configurations were tested. The suction power was adjusted for creating the following pressure values (relative to ambient WT off): -0.25, -0.50, -1.00, and -1.50 PSI. Steady localized suction was tested in the following configurations (here we focus on the most beneficial):

- suction from all the holes,
- suction only from the first row,
- suction only from the third row,
- suction only from 5 holes in the first row at the inboard side (holes 1-5 open),
- suction only from 5 holes in the first row at the outboard side (holes 5-9 open), and
- suction only from 5 holes in the first row at alternating pattern (holes 1,3,5,7,9 open).

To visualize the wake structure downstream of the model, two so-called “seven-hole probes” were installed on a traverse in the WT. The probes were fabricated and calibrated at TAU [1]. Seven-hole probe devices are 3mm diameter device which measure pressure from 7 holes. Those pressures can be translated into three velocity components, static and total pressure. The probes were mounted on a 2D traverse system which can move the probes in two axes, y and z, normal to the free-

stream direction. With these two axes motion, the flow in almost the entire wind tunnel cross section can be scanned. This setup enables to investigate the wake structure behind the model. From the in-plane velocity vector, the vorticity component normal to that plane can be calculated for each pair of velocity components. A typical wake scan takes about 12 hours.

3. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

In this section, baseline flow results are presented and discussed. The data includes surface pressures, integrated coefficients, surface flow visualization and wake data. Following the baseline flow description, steady suction is applied and its effects on all the above flow features are presented and discussed.

3.1. The baseline flow

The results for the baseline uncontrolled flow are presented in this section. First, the results from the pressure taps and the aerodynamic lift (from pressure distributions) will be discussed. Later, surface flow visualization with tufts and oil was to support the results from the pressure taps are discussed. The wake downstream of the model was mapped with the seven-hole probes. Pressure distributions on the airfoil surface were examined to obtain understanding of the flow behaviour over the wing. The focus is on the AoA range of 8-16 degrees and in particular in AoA=11,12 degrees in which flow detachment is expected from the CFD simulations. Surface pressure distribution (C_p) measurements in the inboard and outboard cross sections is presented together with a spanwise cross section in the front and back of the main element. In addition, C_p measurements in the front and back of the expected detachment region near the main element LE, slat cut-out, pylon junction (yellow dots region, according to Figure 5) are presented.

The surface pressure measurements were evaluated for two sections, an inboard section (1) and an outboard section (2), see Figure 5. For the two sections, the lift coefficient was calculated. The lift results for inboard and outboard sections are presented in Figure 7. Stall can be recognized approximately at the range 11-12 degrees angle of attack for both sections.

Figure 7 Lift coefficient, integrated from C_p for the inboard and outboard lines of pressure taps, $U=25\text{m/s}$.

Note that this is only sectional lift and averaged wing lift can be different values but stall angle is not expected to change.

Figure 8 Inboard C_p , $U=25\text{m/s}$ Baseline.

A few pressure coefficients C_p vs. x/c plots are shown for the inboard section (Figure 8), at a few incidence angles corresponding to pre-stall, stall and post stall. This is the section that is close to the expected separation region. The pressure taps on the slat are very close to the slat-edge, and therefore 3D effects cause low acceleration and a rather weak negative C_p created by the slat. For the main element close to the LE, we can see that as the AoA increases the pressure coefficient decreases to a minimum value meaning a higher lift coefficient. After reaching the minimum value, at about AoA=12 deg, one can note an increase in the pressure coefficient on the upper surface close to the LE. This result supports the existence of the stall angle (Figure 7). The slat experiences an increase in the upper surface pressure gradient as AoA increases resulting in higher lift. The flap C_p is not measured downstream of the Inboard C_p s therefore is not shown in Figure 8.

Figure 9 Outboard Cp, U=25m/s Baseline.

Cp vs. x/c measurements for the outboard cross section are shown in Figure 9. This cross section is distant from the expected separation region and it is better “protected” by the slat. The outboard cross section slat is providing $C_p=-4$ and more, experiencing a very small decrease in pressure gradient before reaching $AoA=12$ deg. There is only one cross-section for the flap, the outboard. It is evident that the flap is less loaded for the post stall conditions as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 10 shows Cp plots in the spanwise direction for the entire span, and for the separation prone region (Figure 11). From these two plots it is difficult to infer where separation is taking place, if at all. At the front section Cp decreases while in the rear of the main element, Cp increases. The Cps closer to the LE shown in Figure 11, just indicate higher acceleration as AoA increases, even at post stall ($AoA=12$ deg).

Figure 10 Spanwise Cp, U=25, Baseline.

Figure 11 Detailed spanwise Cp in the separation prone region (yellow dots in Figure 5), inboard of the Pylon, Baseline U=25m/s.

In Figure 12 below we present a CAD rendering of the separation prone region, and under it in Figure 13, a surface oil flow visualization for $AoA=11-12$ deg is shown. The region marked by high concentration of white pigment is characterized by low wall shear stress. It is evident that the flow tends to separate on the inboard side of the pylon, half way to the inboards slat-edge cut out. This is in agreement with the CFD prediction shown in Figure 1 [1].

In Figure 14 we present tuft flow visualization showing downstream directed tufts at $AoA=8$ deg. Localized reverse flow just starts to develop at 10 deg and is significantly enhanced as the AoA is increased to 11 deg and above.

The combined image from the flow visualization indicates separated flow localised to the expected region (as also predicted by CFD), while it also presents the inability of the Cp to clearly indicate separation in this complex 3D flow regime.

Figure 12 A sketch showing the expected separation prone region, marked by red circle on the CAD image.

Figure 13 Surface oil flow visualization image at the slat cut-out region, Baseline AoA=14 deg U=25m/s.

Figure 14 Tufts flow visualization enhanced by UV light, baseline, U=25m/s. The engine pylon connection to the wing is shown on right low corner of the images.

3.2. The effect of steady suction

First, the contribution of each row of suction holes (first and third) was examined in terms of the lift coefficient alternation in comparison to the baseline case (Figure 7). Steady suction was applied at the range of -0.25 psi to -1.5 psi in each row separately. Figure 15 presents the lift coefficient for the inboard cross section versus the angle of attack. For all suction magnitude cases, the first row has greater influence rather than the third row, especially between AoA=11deg to AoA=13deg (stall angles). An exception can be seen for the maximum suction magnitude where the third row has a minor advantage with comparison to the first row. This is reasonable since the significant suction magnitude is capable of better separation delay and in that case the further downstream row becomes more effective. Both the first and the third-suction rows show improvement from the baseline case, at AoA=12deg, ranges between 0.57% to for the -0.25psi suction third row case to 1.75% for the -1.50psi suction third row case. The Outboard cross section presented in Figure 16 shows similar but stronger effects.

Figure 15 Cl vs. AoA for the inboard cross section, for the 1st and 3rd rows suction tests with comparison to the baseline case.

Figure 16 Cl vs. AoA outboard cross section, for the 1st and 3rd rows suction tests with comparison to the baseline case.

Spanwise and flap C_p 's are presented in Figure 17- Figure 19. It is evident that the effect of the first suction row is indeed stronger close to the suction holes (yellow dots, Figure 5). Investigating the effect persists to the flap, and also there the effect of row 1 is stronger.

The tufts flow visualization shown in Figure 21 and Figure 22, confirms the CI indications that separation is being controlled by the steady suction applied from the first row of suction holes effectively. The wool tufts downstream and outboard of the suction holes are significantly stabilized and directed downstream in Figure 22 compared to Figure 21.

Figure 20 The region on which tufts were applied and visualized below.

Figure 17 C_p vs Z , Separation region front, 12 deg.

Figure 18 C_p vs Z , Separation region back, 12 deg.

Figure 19 The flap C_p as affected by -0.5psi suction at $\text{AoA}=12$ deg, first and third suction rows compared.

Figure 21 Baseline, $\text{AoA}=12$ deg, $U=25\text{m/s}$.

Figure 22 1st suction row, all holes open, -1psi , $U=25\text{m/s}$.

Near wake data has been acquired about 1m downstream of the wing trailing edge using seven holes probes in order to study the structure of the near wake, its alternation by flow control, the vortex development and CFD validation.

Figure 23 below presents the baseline near wake at $\text{AoA}=14$ deg and $U=25\text{m/s}$. A complex 3D wake structure is created from the vortical flow emanating from the nacelle and the wing elements and its interaction, especially when the main wing element stalls. The strong velocity deficit on the right ($Y=0.15$; $Z=-0.03$) is created by the outboard corner separation. The addition of suction is characterized in Fig. 24 by the difference between the controlled and baseline streamwise velocity. The beneficial effect of the LE suction is shown by an addition of 15-20% U_x at ($Y=-0.14$, $Z=-0.15$) while other regions suffer some streamwise momentum loss.

Fig. 23 The baseline streamwise velocity, AoA=14 deg, U=25m/s, NO Suction.

Fig. 24 Changes in the streamwise velocity due to suction from all holes of the first row, AoA=14 deg, U=25m/s, Suction pressure -1psi.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

This paper presents a status update on innovative flow control concept, development and application to a generic high lift wing. The target is to control flow separation from the “unprotected” region of the wing leading edge, where a slat cut-out is forced due to large diameter engine installed very close to the wing. Steady suction is applied from an array of holes close to the leading edge. Pressure distributions, integrated lift coefficients and flow visualization confirm the performance benefits predicted also by CFD. The next step of the project involves the application of pulsed blowing downstream of the suction holes, the

development of an SaOB actuator array for the large scale test and its application.

The purpose of this work is to demonstrate that the developed SaOB actuator is capable of compensating the lift degradation caused by the slat cut-out extension by simultaneously meeting mass flow limitations.

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